

Aaron Hugh Braun is the CEO of Willow Creek Capital Management, a privately owned hedge fund sponsor that finances the public equity markets across the United States. He founded Willow Creek Capital Management, a California-based S-Corp in 1994.

This experienced and successful classic long/short manager has actively been involved in the alternative investment arena since 1989. His portfolio management experience began in 1995, nearly 23 years ago, and his expertise evolved over time. This senior-level investor/manager specializes in contrarian and non-consensus strategies for investing. Aaron has distinguished himself as being strong advocate for the pursuit of fundamentally-driven short selling, which enabled his funds to generate positive returns in all down market years since inception, including 2000-2002 and 2007-2008.

His professional investment management activities span for over 28 years, including the 23 years of managing Willow Creek Capital Management activities. He founded the privately owned hedge fund sponsor in 1994 and is still actively involved in all marketing and client service activities. As the CEO of Willow Creek Capital Management, Aaron Hugh Braun determines the overall firm policy and strategic direction, while managing the execution of the firm's business plan on a daily basis. At all times since inception, he has been the sole shareholder and all related entities.

At Willow Creek Capital Management, Aaron Hugh Braun initiated two classic "Jones-model" funds, an offshore fund, a concentrated "long-only" fund and a unique short-biased fund. The company enjoyed the reputation as a premier manager and grew from \$2 million at inception to a peak level of over \$1.3 billion. Clients ranged from high net worth individuals to some of the largest and most respected U.S. and international investors/financial companies.